

COMPUTER PHOBIA AMONG SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS AS RELATED TO THEIR GENDER

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Abstract

In the present study investigator investigate the computer phobia of senior secondary school teacher teaching in senior secondary school in Himachal Pradesh for this investigation The sample included only school teachers teaching in senior secondary schools of Mandi and Kullu Disttt. of Himachal Pradesh. The study was confined to a sample of 400 teachers. The study was restricted to two variables i.e. computer phobia as dependent variable and gender, independent variables. In the present study Computer Phobia Scale constructed and standardized by Dr. Rajasekar and Dr. Vaiyapuri Raja was used by the researcher. Statistics is a mathematical technique or process of gathering, describing, organizing, analysis and interpreting numerical data. The statistical techniques are used to give meaningful and consider picture of the whole data so that it could be easily comprehended. It is employed to test the hypotheses in the study. In order to study the distribution of computer phobia scores of secondary school teachers, descriptive statistics like mean, median, mode, S.D. ,Q.D., skewness and kurtosis was used. For studying the gender-wise, significance of the difference in the computer phobia among school teachers teaching in senior secondary schools, t-test was used and the investigator find that their was no significant difference in the mean scores of overall computer phobia of male and female school teachers teaching in senior secondary schools.

Introduction

Computer has become part and parcel of our life. Almost all our daily activities one way or the other are associated with computer. Almost everyone is having a personal computer in their homes and only a minimum percentage of them are regularly using it. Many of them are rarely using computers due to many reasons and one such reason may be their fear towards using the computer. By and large unknowingly have an irrational fear over this electronic machine and hence they keep the computers as their status symbol. Even many of the teachers have this irrational fear towards computers. This

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irrational fear towards computer is known as “computer phobia”. If a teacher is free from computer phobia, then he can make use of computers during their teaching process without any inhibitions. Computer has revolutionized the education field. In the present progressive era having computer knowledge practically is too much necessary. But there are many persons who fear to perform on computer; this is known as computer phobia. There is no consensus in the literature on the use of the terms such as computer anxiety, computer phobia and technophobia. In the studies performed so far this subject has been handled under some titles, computer phobia, techno stress, cyber phobia, computer aversion, technophobia, and computer anxiety. Although technophobia is becoming a commonly used term, appearing in newspapers and popular magazines with increasing frequency, in a pioneering work, defined computer phobia as: (a) a resistance to talking about computers or even thinking about computers, (b) fear or anxiety toward computers, and (c) hostile or aggressive thoughts about computers. Afterwards, technophobia has come to be known as computer phobia, and has been defined as: “(a) anxiety about present or future interactions with computers or computer related technology, (b) negative global attitudes about computers, and their operation or their societal impact; and/or, (c) specific negative cognitions or self-critical internal dialogues during actual computer interaction or when contemplating future computer interaction.” Computer phobia is an intense fear of something that possesses little or no danger. While people with computer phobia realize that these fears are irrational, they often find that facing or even thinking about facing the fear situation brings on a panic attack. One of the root causes of computer phobia is the rapidity of technological advance. In the present technological society, the impression is that artifacts such as computers are more valued than people. Thus, computer phobia is a particularly striking example of the effects of the rapid growth of a technological society.

Cantrell & Wong (1999) defined computer anxiety, which has often been linked computer phobia, refers to negative feelings associated with the use of computers.

Jay (1981) defined computer phobia as the negative attitude toward computers that results from computer anxiety.

Rosen and Weil (1992) further defined computer phobia as anxiety and a negative attitude toward present and future interactions with computers.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The problem selected for research may be defined as under.

“A STUDY OF COMPUTER PHOBIA AMONG SCHOOL TEACHERS TEACHING IN SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN RELATION TO THEIR GENDER”

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study was conducted to achieve the following objectives.

1. To study gender-wise difference in computer phobia among school teachers teaching in senior secondary schools with respect to:

- i. Personal Failure
- ii. Human Vs. Machine Ambiguity
- iii. Convenience

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

In the present study following hypotheses were formulated.

1. There will be no significant gender-wise difference in computer phobia among school teachers teaching in senior secondary schools with respect to:

- i. Personal Failure
- ii. Human Vs. Machine Ambiguity
- iii. Convenience

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The present study was delimited to the following aspects.

- ❖ The sample included only school teachers teaching in senior secondary schools of Mandi and Kullu Distt. of Himachal Pradesh.
- ❖ The study was confined to a sample of 400 teachers.
- ❖ The study was restricted to two variables i.e. computer phobia as dependent variable and gender, independent variables.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS OF TERMS USED

Following terms have been used in the study.

1. Computer Phobia: Computer phobia is a fear or dislike of advanced technology. It invokes a wide range of negative emotions, such as anxiety, incompetence, fear, stress and nervousness. It not only creates psychological imbalances but shifts human nature from reality. In the present study the level of computer phobia among teachers was assessed by ‘Computer Phobia Scale’ developed and standardized by Dr. S. Rajasekar and Dr. P. Vaiyapuri.

2. Senior Secondary School Teachers: It refers to the teachers teaching in government senior secondary schools of Distt. Kullu and Mandi of Himachal Pradesh.

3. Gender: Male and female teachers teaching in govt. and private senior secondary school.

RESEARCH METHOD USED

In order to accomplish the objective of the present study, the descriptive survey method was considered appropriately for gathering data computer phobia among secondary school teachers. Descriptive survey method is designed to obtain pertinent and precise information concerning the current status of phenomena and whenever possible to draw valid general conclusion from the facts discovered. Descriptive research involves events that present condition. It aims to describe “what exists” with respect to variables or conditions or conditions in a situation.

SAMPLING

Some populations are so large that their study would be expansive in terms of time, money, efforts and manpower. Sampling is one of the most important and indispensable factor of every research study. Sampling is a process by which relatively small number of individuals, objects or events is selected and analyzed in order to find out something about the target population from which the representative sample was selected. Sampling has been increasingly used in educational research for answering certain questions about a specific population. The sample drawn out of population should be true representative of the population otherwise; the results of the study may turn to be futile. The representative proportion of the population is called a sample.

In the present investigation, a representative sample of 400 school teachers teaching in senior secondary schools was selected from district Mandi and Kullu of Himachal Pradesh by using convenient sampling technique.

TOOL USED

In the present study Computer Phobia Scale constructed and standardized by Dr. Rajasekar and Dr. Vaiyapuri Raja was used by the researcher.

DATA ANALYSIS

Statistics is a mathematical technique or process of gathering, describing, organizing, analysis and interpreting numerical data. The statistical techniques are used to give meaningful and consider picture of the whole data so that it could be easily comprehended. It is employed to test the hypotheses in the study. In order to study the distribution of computer phobia scores of secondary school teachers, descriptive statistics like mean, median, mode, S.D. ,Q.D., skewness and kurtosis was used. For studying the gender-wise, significance of the difference in the computer phobia among school teachers teaching in senior secondary schools, t-test was used.

5.2 CONCLUSIONS

From the analysis and interpretation of the data, following conclusions may be drawn.

‘t’ Value Showing Significance of Difference in Mean Scores of ‘Components of Computer Phobia’ and ‘Overall Computer Phobia’ of Senior Secondary School Teachers in relation to their Gender

Sr. No.	Dimension	Male	Female	d _f	SE _D	t-value
1.	Personal failure	N= 185	N= 190	373	0.754	1.075 ^{NS}
		Mean=30.78	Mean=31.59			
		SD=7.089	SD=7.501			
2.	Human Vs. Machine Ambiguity	N= 185	N= 190	373	0.470	0.64 ^{NS}
		Mean= 20.45	Mean=20.48			
		SD= 4.440	SD= 4.664			
3.	Convenience	N= 185	N= 190	373	0.515	1.046 ^{NS}
		M= 23.72	M=24.26			
		SD=4.990	SD=4.981			
4.	Overall Computer Phobia	N= 185	N= 190	373	1.432	0.942 ^{NS}

- ❖ Male and female senior secondary school teachers do not differ significantly with respect to their personal failure.

Gender-wise Difference among Senior Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Personal Failure

- ❖ Male and female senior secondary school teachers do not differ significantly with respect to human vs machine ambiguity.

Gender-wise Difference among Senior Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Human Vs Machine Ambiguity

- ❖ Male and female senior secondary school teachers do not differ significantly with respect to their convenience.

Gender-wise Difference among Senior Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Convenience

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

The results of the present study have following implications for education:

- Results of the present study revealed that male teachers teaching in senior secondary schools have higher mean scores of Personal Failure component of computer phobia than their female counterparts. It means that female teachers have higher Personal Failure computer phobia than male teachers. But the difference between the two groups is not statistically significant. Government should appoint computer trained teachers or the teacher, who have practical knowledge of computer. Having seen the importance and necessity of computer in present era, the computer practical and theoretic paper should to be compulsory for all professional course, whether management, B.Ed. or others as medical, technology etc. For removing the anxiety about present or future interactions with computers or computer related technology female teachers have to devote some time for working with computers daily.

- Positive global attitude should be there about computers, their operations, or their societal impact.
- Educationists should make female teachers clear about the importance of computer in life. They should remove the fear of computer from teachers' mind and make them understand that it is not too hard to work on it. They should give teachers in their practical work of computer and if they see that there are some computer phobic than they should take their extra class of computer's practical and give them appropriate guidance to remove their fear of computer.
- Teacher trainees are suggested to take computer knowledge as an essential part of their study. Only theoretic knowledge is not sufficient for it, they should know practical knowledge of computer also.
- Teachers should be motivated to get training in the use of IT. It can be done with the help of various types of workshops, seminars, orientations programs and refresher courses for teachers which will develop in them positive and favourable attitude towards information technology and computer.
- Individual training should be given through chat base online or web-based therapy which can develop in teachers a positive attitude towards web self-efficacy, perceive web enjoyment, and behavioral intention to use the web in order to remove the phobia.
- Teachers need to be prompted to make use of internet for updating their knowledge and general awareness.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER STUDY

A few suggestions for further research having put forward as under

- In this study only one district has been selected, it can be done on state level, national level and international level.
- This study has been done only on the teachers while it can be carried out on other employees also.
- This study may be conducted on post graduate teachers. Similar study can be conducted on teachers at other levels of education with the help of questionnaire according to their level.
- The study may be conducted by taking sample from other districts of the state.

- A comparative study of computer phobia among tribal and non-tribal school teachers may be done.
- A study can be undertaken to find out the effect of psychological factors on attitude of teachers towards computer and information technology.

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